
**Automation and Employee Work-Life Balance: Evidence from Gujarat Information
Technology Companies**

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DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21206907

Abstract:

The widespread use of automation technology such as AI, digital workflow systems, etc., has altered the operational landscape of Information Technology (IT) organizations. While automation improves organization efficiency and productivity; it also presents an opportunity to investigate its impact on employee's wellbeing. This study is conducted to determine the impact of automation on employee's work life balance, in particular IT companies located in Gujarat. Also, this study will look at how automation affects employees' job stress, and what is the relationship between job stress and work-life balance. This study adopts a quantitative methodology employing a cross-sectional survey method. Primary data were obtained by way of a structured questionnaire from eighty employees who are working in various IT companies across Gujarat, through Google Forms. Convenience sampling was used and responses were based on a five-point Likert scale. Data analysis was carried out using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS 4 software.

Keywords: Automation, Artificial Intelligence, Job Stress, Work-Life Balance, IT Companies, Employee Well-Being.

Introduction

As we enter into a world where artificial intelligence is becoming common in the workplace including machine learning, robotic process automation and smart software — automation will continue to be a central part of how businesses operate. In addition to the benefits of being able to automate repetitive functions and make decisions based upon data and analytics, automation also allows businesses to develop applications more efficiently and to deliver better services to customers.[1]

Automation does offer employees several advantages. By automating some of the routine aspects of jobs, employees are able to spend less time on mundane or uninteresting tasks. They are then free to concentrate on other areas of their jobs and possibly take on more challenging responsibilities. Additionally, employees are able to complete their assigned tasks faster and more efficiently. This results in lower levels of employee stress, more effective job performance and reduced risk of work-related injury. Research suggests that when employees work in environments where automation and artificial intelligence play a major role, they tend to experience improved well-being and work/life balance.[15] However, there are downsides associated with automation. Many employees who are impacted by automation have to continually update their skills to remain employable in today's rapidly evolving economy. It is also not uncommon for employees whose employers are heavily dependent on advanced technologies to find it difficult to separate their work from their personal

lives.[3] The use of digital platforms for communicating with colleagues, being monitored remotely via automated systems and using remote-based tools to access company resources, can lead to an expectation of being available 24/7. Therefore, issues surrounding job stress, burn-out and achieving a healthy work/life balance have become increasingly prevalent within this type of environment.

These are just a few examples of what is happening in various regions around the world. Because each region tends to have different types of industries and different ways in which they utilize technology in their workplaces, it would be beneficial to examine regional-specific research so that the needs of workers in those specific locations could be met appropriately. For example, in countries like India and China, the information technology (IT) sector employs millions of people. Cities like Ahmedabad, Gandhinagar, Surat and Vadodara in Gujarat have attracted a large number of IT companies and technology start-ups.[8]

Work-Life Balance and Employee Wellbeing and Organizational Performance. Work-Life Balance is defined as an employee's ability to be able to work and meet all personal obligations without being overwhelmed by conflicting demands from each area. When there is a healthy work-life balance, it leads to better job satisfaction, improved mental health, positive relationships with families, and a sense of commitment to one's employer. However, when an individual experiences a poor work-life balance, they typically suffer from high levels of stress, burn out, missed days at work (absenteeism), reduced productivity, and an increase in the likelihood of leaving the organization.[6] As many IT workers now experience pressure to complete projects with short timelines, deal with heavy workloads, and continually learn new technologies, finding ways to maintain a healthy work-life balance has become a major issue for both employees and organizations. One of the most critical elements affecting work-life balance in today's technology-based workplaces is job related stress. Stress resulting from working conditions creates psychological and/or physical harm to an employee when they feel they do not possess sufficient resources or capabilities to adequately fulfil workplace requirements. With more and more automation taking place in industries throughout the world and increased usage of digital technologies, individuals are facing greater amounts of stress due to increasing pressures and complexities associated with performing their jobs. Studies examining techno-stress indicate that technology-based stressors can negatively affect employees' work-life balances and overall emotional wellbeing. Individuals who continue to find themselves unable to adjust to rapid technological advancements will likely begin to experience emotional fatigue, anxiety, and eventually burn-out; leading to issues with their personal lives and quality of life.[13] Automation and the potential effects on employee work-life balance are also multi-dimensional. Automation has the capacity to enhance employee productivity and flexibility but could create additional sources of stress and work-life challenges if it is poorly designed/implemented.[9] Thus far, prior studies have generated mixed results concerning how automation influences employee wellbeing.

On the one hand, some researchers believe that automation improves work-life balance by eliminating mundane tasks and providing employees with alternative methods for completing their duties and balancing their lifestyles.[10] Conversely, other researchers contend that automation can lead to technostress/burnout due to constant communication requirements. This disparity in findings emphasizes the necessity for conducting further empirical investigations – especially focusing on particular geographic regions/industries. Although automation is becoming increasingly prominent in the IT sector in Gujarat, very few empirical studies have investigated how automation affects employee work-life balance within this region. Most prior studies have emphasized assessing how automation impacts organizational performance/performance metrics (i.e., technological adoption/productivity); however, much less emphasis has been placed on studying employee

wellbeing. Additionally, the function that job stress performs in mediating the relationship between automation and work-life balance has not yet received adequate attention. Therefore, understanding these interactions is essential since employee wellbeing directly relates to an organization's ability to produce goods/services efficiently/innovatively, retain skilled staff members, and ultimately achieve long term sustainability. Consequently, this current study intends to assess the direct effects of automation on employee work-life balance in Gujarat-based IT firms. Furthermore, this study will examine the indirect effects of automation on employee job stress and whether or not job stress has an effect on an employee's ability to attain/maintain a healthy work-life balance.[5] Utilizing SmartPLS-SEM to analyze collected data, this study aims to empirically support theories explaining the causal relationships between automation, job stress and work-life balance. Ultimately, this research is expected to add to the current body of knowledge while developing practical recommendations for managers/policymakers interested in promoting technological development while maintaining employee wellbeing.

Literature Review

Automation

Automation encompasses using technology (artificial intelligence or "AI"), machine learning ("ML") and/or Robotic Process Automation ("RPA") to carry out a variety of tasks with very little direct involvement from humans. For businesses looking to increase their operational efficiency, decrease their operating expense, create higher productivity levels and remain competitive in rapidly changing markets, automation has become a key strategic option. Organizations are able to optimize their workflow; reduce the number of mistakes made by humans; and improve the quality of services they provide through automation.[12]

IT organizations have widely adopted automation throughout their operations including in areas such as software development, software testing, customer service, cyber security, cloud computing and business process management.[4] As organizations increasingly adopt AI-based applications and RPA-based tools, there are being significant changes to both the jobs that people do at work and how those jobs will be performed. Based upon research conducted by Schwabe & Castellacci (2020), it was determined that automation has positive effects on the productivity of employees and their job satisfaction due to its ability to eliminate repetitive tasks and enable employees to spend more time on higher value-added activities. On the other hand, many employees feel concerned about their future employment opportunities because of automation. Researchers Narayanan et al. (2026) concluded that when employees are working in environments where AI is used to assist them, they are able to perform better and produce greater efficiencies. At the same time, there are potential additional issues created for employees in terms of adapting to their workplace.[7]

Employee Work-Life Balance

Work-Life Balance is defined as a person's capability to successfully manage their professional obligations/commitments and personal responsibilities without creating conflict in either domain (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011).[10] A good work-life balance is recognized as an important indicator of employee satisfaction, and quality of life. Maintaining a healthy work-life balance enables employees to better protect their physical and mental health; develop stronger family bonds; and ultimately enhance their job satisfaction. Employees that have achieved a good work-life balance generally exhibit improved productivity, organizational commitment, and engagement (Ali & Siddiqui, 2026);[2] however, poor work-life balance leads to burnout, emotional exhaustion, absenteeism, and turnover intentions. As technology increases throughout the workplace, achieving and maintaining

work-life balance is becoming increasingly difficult for many employees. This increased difficulty is primarily due to the constant availability required to utilize digital platforms for communication and access to remote working arrangements. Although automation may provide employees with reduced workloads and greater flexibility in how they complete tasks; it may also create blurred lines between an employees' work and personal time by requiring employees to be accessible outside of regular business hours.[11]

Job Stress

Stress at Work: An Overview of What Creates Stress Job stress refers to the psychological and physical responses to the strain created by the amount of work expected from a person and their ability to deal with it (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). In the Information Technology field, there are many stressful situations related to; deadlines, technical changes, workload, and meeting expectations. There are several contributing factors toward creating stress in the workplace. Some common ones include; heavy workload, role confusion, job uncertainty, lack of organizational support, and technological complexity. As Automation and Artificial Intelligence continue to evolve in our world, we can expect employees' fears about losing their jobs and adapting to new ways of working will add to the stress they experience.[9]

Research Gap

The review of existing literature identifies several research gaps. First, most studies examining automation and employee outcomes have been conducted in developed countries or broader industrial settings, with limited attention given to Gujarat-based IT companies. Consequently, there is insufficient empirical evidence regarding how automation influences employees within Gujarat's rapidly growing IT sector.

Second, previous studies have largely focused on organizational performance, technological adoption, and job satisfaction, whereas fewer studies have examined the combined relationship among automation, job stress, and work-life balance. Understanding these relationships is essential because employee well-being directly influences organizational effectiveness.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The purpose of this research study will be to investigate the association between automation and job-related anxiety and an employee's ability to achieve work/life balance in Gujarat IT firms through the use of a quantitative methodology. The reason that a quantitative methodology was selected as most appropriate for this study is the collection of numerical data with the statistical analysis of associations between variables. The current study utilized a cross-sectional survey methodology where data were obtained from participants at one particular point in time. Cross-sectional methodologies are commonly employed in organizational/behavioral studies to assess employees' views/experiences concerning the effects of automation on their work life balance as they relate to their organization's contemporary work environment.

Population & Sample size of the Study

The target population for this study comprises employees working in Information Technology (IT) companies located in Gujarat, India. The population includes professionals employed in various job roles such as software developers, software engineers, system analysts, project managers, technical

support executives, quality assurance professionals, and other IT-related positions. These employees are considered appropriate respondents because they are directly exposed to automation technologies, artificial intelligence tools, and digital work environments. A sample size of 80 respondents is proposed for the study.

Sampling Technique

This study employed convenience sampling as one type of nonprobability sampling. Nonprobability samples are those where the sample selection is determined by factors other than chance (e.g., respondent availability). A nonprobability sample was chosen due to the fact that creating an exhaustive sampling frame of all IT workers in Gujarat would be very challenging and time consuming. In addition, using a nonprobability sample will allow the researcher to obtain responses from people who are currently working in the IT industry, and therefore available. While using a nonprobability sample may restrict the ability to generalize results, it has been found to be effective in many types of organizational and exploratory studies.

Data Collection Method

Primary data were gathered from a structured questionnaire that assessed employee views about automation, job pressures, and work/life. The Google Forms platform provided an inexpensive way to collect the information from multiple IT companies in the state of Gujarat. Using the internet to obtain responses is helpful since it makes participation easy, allows for quicker data gathering, and easier data processing. Respondents will be asked if they want to voluntarily take part, and to answer as honestly as possible based on their experience.

Measurement Scale

The study utilizes a five-point Likert scale to measure respondents' level of agreement with the questionnaire statements. The scale ranges from:

- 1 = Strongly Disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Neutral
- 4 = Agree
- 5 = Strongly Agree

The Likert scale is one of the most widely used measurement instruments in social science and management research because it enables respondents to express the intensity of their opinions and perceptions in a simple and structured manner. The use of a five-point scale facilitates data analysis and is compatible with SmartPLS-SEM techniques for assessing relationships among constructs.

Data Analysis Technique

Data that is gathered will be analyzed via SmartPLS 4. There are two parts to this process. First, we will use the SmartPLS program to analyze the measurement model. This portion of the evaluation will look at the reliability and validity of our measure. We will look at various indicators which include, but are not limited to: Factor Loadings; Cronbach's Alpha; Composite Reliability (CR); Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all of these. Second, we will examine the structural model by looking at how automation effects job stress and job stress affects work life balance. For the structural model, we will also calculate path coefficients, t-values, p-values and R-squared values. In order to

determine whether or not the relationship between automation, job stress and work/life balance is statistically significant, we will perform bootstrapping on the results (Hair et al., 2022).[16]

Table no- 1

Source: SmartPLS Output

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
Automation	0.908	0.918	0.786
Job Stress	0.864	0.914	0.706
Work Life Balance	0.875	0.886	0.725

Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) were assessed to establish internal consistency and convergent validity. The results satisfied the recommended criteria suggested by Hair et al. (2022), indicating that the measurement model possesses acceptable reliability and validity.

Therefore, the constructs included in the study were considered appropriate for further structural model assessment.

Results and Discussion

Demographic profile Analysis

Table no- 2

Source: SPSS Output

1. Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	35	43.8	43.8	43.8
	Male	45	56.3	56.3	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table no- 3

Source: SPSS Output

2. Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	66	82.5	82.5	82.5
	31-40	13	16.3	16.3	98.8
	41-50	1	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table no- 4

Source: SPSS Output

3. Educational Qualification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Graduate	26	32.5	32.5	32.5
	Others	7	8.8	8.8	41.3
	Phd	5	6.3	6.3	47.5
	Postgraduate	42	52.5	52.5	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table no- 5

Source: SPSS Output

4. Work Experience

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2-5 years	13	16.3	16.3	16.3
	6-10 years	10	12.5	12.5	28.7
	Less than 2 years	48	60.0	60.0	88.8
	More than years	109	11.3	11.3	100.0
	Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Table no – 6

Source: SPSS Output

5. Job Position

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	HR/Administratio n	3	3.8	3.8	3.8
	Others	50	62.5	62.5	66.3
	Project Manager	9	11.3	11.3	77.5

Software Developer	6	7.5	7.5	85.0
Team Leader	12	15.0	15.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	100.0	

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographics

The demographics of participants in this study were evaluated to characterize the employees involved in the research. Eighty participants from IT firms in Gujarat responded to the survey. Gender, Age, Education Level, Work Experience and Job Title were among the demographic parameters assessed.

Gender

In terms of gender-based data on the number of men and women responding to the questionnaire; 45 (56.3 percent) of respondents were males, whereas 35 (43.8 percent) were females. Data thus reveal that there is an almost even split between male and female employees in terms of percentage participation in the sample. While it appears that males somewhat exceeded females in the sample, the almost equal number of each gender suggests that there is sufficient variation to assess differing viewpoints about automation, job pressure and work/life balance of employees in Gujarat IT firms.

Age

According to the ages of the respondents 82.5% or 66 employees were in their twenties, i.e., between twenty-one and thirty years of age. 16.3 % or 13 employees were between thirty-one and forty years old. Only 1 employee (1.3 percent), was between forty-one and fifty years of age. Thus, the data suggest that the sample is composed primarily of young employees in the Gujarat IT sector. Given that so many young employees are currently employed in technology driven sectors and have been exposed to automation technology; the data will provide insight into the attitudes and experiences of young IT professionals.

Education Level

A review of the education levels of respondents indicated that more than half or 42 respondents (52.5 percent) were post-graduates. Graduates comprised 32.5 percent or 26. 5 respondents (6.3 percent) held Ph.D.'s, and 7 respondents (8.8 %) fell into another educational category. Thus, the data indicate that more than half of the employees in Gujarat's IT sector hold degrees at the graduate level or above. The prevalence of post-graduates in the sample demonstrates the need for specialized education to perform jobs in the IT sector. An educated workforce can also better appreciate and adapt to automation technology.

Experience

Data on respondents' years of experience showed that 60% (or 48) of respondents had less than two years of work experience. 16.3% percent (or 13) of respondents had 2–5 years of experience, 12.5 % (10) had six-to-ten years of experience, and 11.3% (9) had over ten years of experience. Thus, these data demonstrate that a sizeable portion of the sample consisted of relatively inexperienced workers in India's IT sector. Since the dominant segment of the sample are first-time professionals in the IT industry, they may be more susceptible to adapting to changing workplace conditions related to automation but they may also face additional challenges when adjusting to automated workplaces.

Job Title

Respondent distribution based upon job title demonstrated that the most prevalent category was "others" which accounted for 50 (62.5%). 12(15%) identified themselves as team leaders.9 (11.3%) identified themselves as project managers. 6 (7.5%) self-identified as software developers. 3 respondents (3.8%) reported being in HR/administrative positions. Overall, these results suggest that respondents are representative of a wide range of functional areas within IT organizations. The predominance of employees classified as "others" implies the existence of numerous specialized technical/operational functions outside those specifically mentioned in the questionnaire. The diversity provided by these classifications increases the representativeness of the sample and offers additional information regarding how employees perceive automation and work-life balance across different types of employment.[7] Overall, the demographic evaluation demonstrates that most respondents are young, highly educated and relatively inexperienced employees working in various capacities within Gujarat IT organizations. Males marginally out-numbered females in response rates and post-graduate degree holders made up nearly all educational backgrounds found among respondents. As such, demographic attributes indicate that the study reflects mainly opinions and experiences of young, educated IT professionals that function in technology-rich work environments and are directly impacted by an organization's use of automation technologies.

Measurement Model Assessment

Figure no- 1

Source: SmartPLS Output

Before examining structural relationships, the reliability and validity of the measurement model were assessed. All indicators had factor loadings above the suggested threshold value (0.7), which is considered to be adequately reliable. Automation ranged from .814 to .925; job stress ranged from .763 to .891; Work-Life Balance ranged from .826 to .883. These values support that all indicators are proper representations for their respective constructs.

Structural Model Assessment

The structural model for this study was analyzed via Bootstrapping in SmartPLS 4. The model looked at the associations between Automation, Job Stress and Work-Life Balance. To determine how well the Structural Model explained the variance of the dependent variables, R-squared (R^2) was used. Results show that Automation accounts for 26.4 % of the variance in Job Stress ($R^2 = .264$), thus indicating that automation is an important predictor of employee job stress in Gujarat IT firms. The combination of Automation and Job Stress together account for 39.8 % of the variance in Work-Life Balance ($R^2 = .398$). As per Hair et al. (2022), both values represent moderate prediction capability of the proposed model. Lastly, the Bootstrapping Results were evaluated with Path Coefficients (β), t-Values and P- Values. A relationship was deemed statistically significant if the T value exceeded 1.96 and the P Value was $< .05$.

Objective-wise Analysis

Objective 1: To examine the impact of automation on employee work-life balance

The main purpose of this research, the initial goal was to assess how automation impacts an employee's work-life balance. The data collected clearly show there is a positive correlation between Automation and Work-Life Balance ($t = 10.080$, $\beta = .677$, $p = 0.000$). The positive sign of the coefficient shows that implementing automation technology has a positive effect on an employee's work-life balance. Since automation replaces or reduces the number of routine tasks an employee performs and improves their job performance, employees can better focus on personal and family matters. As such, it appears that employees will be able to maintain both their professional and personal commitments due to the impact of automation on their work life.

Objective 2: To analyze the effect of automation on employee job stress

The second goal sought to explore how technology could affect worker stress at work. Results indicated a statistically significant positive correlation between Automation and Work Stress ($\beta = .514$, $t = 6.296$, $p = .00$). Results show that increases in automation can have an impact on the amount of stress workers are experiencing. While automation has many benefits for organizations, it may add more stress to the job and make changes to what they need to do at work. Therefore, automation will be one of the most important factors that determine how much stress there is at work.

Objective 3: To examine the impact of job stress on work-life balance

Job stress does not have a significant effect on work-Life balance among employees in this study. The third objective was to evaluate whether an association exists for the impact of job stress on employees' work-Life balance. In accordance with expectations, there were findings that suggested that as employees experienced more job-related stress; they experienced less work-Life balance. Statistically however, this relationship did not achieve significance ($p = .371$) or show any correlation ($\beta = -.102$, $t = .895$).

Hypothesis Testing Results

Table no- 7

Source: SmartPLS

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path Coefficient (β)	T-value	P-value	Decision
H1	Automation \rightarrow Job Stress	0.514	6.296	0.000	Accepted

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path Coefficient (β)	T-value	P-value	Decision
H2	Automation \rightarrow Work-Life Balance	0.677	10.080	0.000	Accepted
H3	Job Stress \rightarrow Work-Life Balance	-0.102	0.895	0.371	Rejected

H1: Automation significantly affects employee job stress

Results indicate a statistically significant positive relationship for Automation with Job Stress ($t=6.296$ $\beta= .514$; $p=.00$) since the t value (6.296) exceeded the critical t of 1.96 for 99% confidence interval and the p value (.00) was smaller than .05. Thus, H1 is confirmed by the data. Results also indicate that technology has an influence upon job-related stress at work. As employees are expected to continue to learn in order to adapt their skills to changing environments created by new technologies, this can be viewed as stressful by many employees.

H2: Automation significantly affects employee work-life balance

The relationship between automation and employees' work-life balance was found to be positively related as well as to be statistically significant with a beta coefficient (β) of .677, and an associated T-statistic (t) of 10.08, and also had a statistical significance of $p = .00$.

H3: Job stress significantly affects employee work-life balance

There is a significant statistical correlation of a negative nature between Job Stress and Work-Life Balance as evidenced by the $\beta = -0.102$; $t = 0.895$; $p = 0.371$. The t value < 1.96 and the p-value $> .05$ suggest the rejection of H3. This indicates there are no significant correlations for job stress to predict work life balance among employees employed in Gujarat IT Companies.

Discussion

These results offer valuable insight for understanding how automation affects relationships among job stress and work-life balance at the IT firms in Gujarat. Automation had a positive impact on work-life balance. These results are consistent with prior research indicating that automation provides employees greater efficiency, lessens routine tasks and thus enables them to spend more time engaged in personal/family related activities. The size of the coefficient ($\beta = .677$) shows that automation has a considerable effect on an individual's work-life balance. Automation increased job-related stress. The current results also reflect similar outcomes based upon research regarding technological adaptation and techno-stress; employees may feel pressured when they adapt to technology changes in addition to additional workplace demands. Employees can develop skills necessary to meet new demands using new technology, however this is perceived as challenging by many employees and therefore continues to require "learning" and skill development.

Although there were expected results; job stress was not found to be a factor of significance affecting work-life balance. There are other examples of previous studies where job-related stress was one of the factors used to determine work-life imbalances. An example of why these two variables is correlated differently than previously researched could include flexible working arrangements available to employees in IT firms in Gujarat, or the availability of supportive organizational systems and/or strategies that help employees cope with stressful conditions in order to minimize the impact of those stresses on employees' quality of life. Therefore, the current findings indicate that automation

can play two roles. For instance, automation allows for more efficient use of an individual's time; ultimately providing better work-life balance. However, it creates job-related stress because employees must continue to learn new technology. As such, firms need to provide training opportunities for employees as well as counselling and stress reduction programs for employees undergoing technological transformations in order to maximize the benefits associated with automation while minimizing its detrimental effects.

Conclusion of Findings

Automation technology is transforming how work is done in Information Technology (IT) organizations. For example, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Robotic Process Automation (RPA), and Digital Tools are changing how employees perform tasks. Thus, understanding the effects of automation on employees' well-being in IT organizations is now crucial. The present study analyzed the influence of automation on employee Work-Life Balance (WLB) and employee Job Stress (JS). It was conducted using structural equation modeling (SmartPLS-SEM).[16]

The Results show that automation has a statistically significant positive relationship with WLB. Participants believed that automation helped reduce the number of repetitive tasks they performed and improve their ability to accomplish their jobs efficiently. These improvements enabled participants to have more time for their families and other personal activities, improving their overall quality of life. Similarly, results indicate that automation had a statistically significant relationship with Job Stress.[9] On one hand, automation has enhanced productivity and improved organizational performance. However, to achieve its full potential, employees are required to constantly learn about new technologies and develop additional skills. Learning to operate and adapt to new technologies can cause anxiety and pressure among employees. Hence, automation can be seen as either an opportunity or a challenge depending upon how it is used in an organization. Results indicate that there is no statistically significant relationship between JS and WLB. Although there was a negative relationship between JS and WLB, the test statistics showed no statistical significance.[3] This indicates that employees of IT companies located in Gujarat India may possess successful coping mechanisms; employer-based supports; or flexible work options that enable them to deal with high levels of stress at work but maintain a good quality of life outside of work. In turn, JS does not appear to be a key contributor to employee WLB according to the data collected from this study.

The Results from hypothesis testing support all of the previous findings. The first hypothesis stated that automation would have a statistically significant effect on JS. Results supported this hypothesis. Similarly, the second hypothesis stated that automation would have a statistically significant effect on WLB. Results again supported this hypothesis. Finally, the third hypothesis suggested that JS would have a statistically significant effect on WLB. Since results were non-significant, this hypothesis was rejected.

Also Results suggest that automation will continue to play a critical role in shaping the experience of employees who work in IT companies located in Gujarat India. While automation can contribute to an improvement in WLB through increased efficiency and reduced routine work, it also contributes to high levels of JS associated with adapting to new technologies. Organizations should therefore implement employee development plans; technical support systems; and stress management programs so that employees can benefit from the efficiencies provided by automation and maintain their well-being. These efforts will ultimately lead to greater organizational success and employee satisfaction.

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